

ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DUNHUANG MURALS AND STAGE SCENERY IN MUSIC ART

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Abstract

The dance, music, and painting forms of different periods in Dunhuang murals are subtly related to the Xinjiang region. The author mainly takes the perspective of music culture as the entry point, and explores the pipa instruments and Hu Xuan dance that often appear in Dunhuang murals as bridges between Xinjiang and Dunhuang murals, in order to better promote China's traditional culture, The widespread dissemination of the unique ethnic music culture in Xinjiang is also the result we hope to see.

Keywords: Dunhuang murals; Xinjiang Minority Music; contact.

Introduction:

The music and dance from different historical periods depicted in Dunhuang murals are precious treasures left to future generations. From the diverse styles of Dunhuang murals, we can deeply appreciate the cultural heritage brought by the ethnic music of the Western Regions, which is the crystallization of the wisdom of ancient people. Next, the author will take Dunhuang murals as the main content, and elaborate in detail on their historical background, mural content, and some musical elements contained therein. It is hoped that the opinions and suggestions proposed by the author can be beneficial to relevant researchers.

1. Historical background

(1) Xinjiang

In ancient history, Xinjiang was often replaced by the Western Regions. Since the Han Dynasty, it has become a territory under the jurisdiction of the central government. From an objective perspective, Xinjiang is a region with numerous ethnic and cultural exchanges. According to relevant data statistics, nearly 50 ethnic minorities once lived in Xinjiang, such as the Tiele, Kangju, Tuhuluo, Gaoche, and so on. Among them, the more representative ethnic groups are the Uyghur The Wusun ethnic group and so on. The history and culture of Xinjiang region are very long, with nomadic, commercial, and agricultural cultures as the main forms. Due to the unique geographical location of Xinjiang, the culture of the region is also very rich and colorful. Taking music culture as an example, Zhang Jian brought the music culture of the Western Regions back to the Central Plains region during the Silk Road, and it was widely loved by people, Among them, the most representative works include "Maha Dule" and other famous pieces such as "Kanguo Music" and "Qiuci Music" played in the Tang Dynasty palace were also created and introduced by the Kangju and Qiuci ethnic groups in the Western Regions.

(2) Dunhuang

Since the early Western Han Dynasty, the Xiongnu people have repeatedly invaded Hexi, forcing the Yue clan people who originally lived in Hexi to migrate. As a result, the entire Hexi region has gradually become the territory of the Xiongnu people. During the reign of Emperor Wu of Han, Zhang Jian was sent to the Western Regions multiple times to assess rebellion,

and then the Silk Road was launched. The Silk Road is mainly divided into two routes, one is the southern route, starting from Dunhuang, passing through Loulan, Congling, Anxi The other is the Northern Line, which still starts from Dunhuang and passes through places such as Gaochang, Qiuci, and Dawan along the way. This shows that Dunhuang played a crucial role in the passage of China's Silk Road, and the Western Regions also have a very close connection with Dunhuang. The modern Western Regions mainly refer to the western region of Xinjiang, which is bounded by Yumen Pass, Therefore, we can further understand the mutual connection between Dunhuang and Xinjiang from a historical perspective.

(3) Dunhuang murals

There are two main types of character images in Dunhuang murals, namely deity images and layman images. Although these two different character images are created based on people's real life, there are significant differences between the two in essence, which are reflected in the following aspects: firstly, at the level of character modeling, the shape of deity images is relatively exaggerated and there are few changes, The image of ordinary people shows relatively obvious characteristics of the times, and their lives are flexible; Secondly, at the level of character costumes, the deity images are mostly dominated by foreign costumes, while the secular costumes are mainly Han costumes; Thirdly, at the level of halo dyeing, divine images are often haloed using the Western Regions method, while secular images are usually haloed using the Central Plains method. Although the visual and cultural experiences brought by Dunhuang murals in different periods vary slightly, as a treasure of Chinese art, the artistic value reflected by Dunhuang brushstrokes cannot be measured.

2. Mural content connection

(1) Dance part

In theory, dance is accompanied by music, so we can also convert some dances on Dunhuang murals into musical tunes for appreciation. Based on relevant data statistics, we can know that there are many types of dances involved in Dunhuang murals, and the painters have superb skills. The tasks drawn not only have their own unique aesthetic sense, At the same time, it can together form an exquisite and unparalleled mural from

an overall perspective. At the same time, painters also attach great importance to depicting the details of these dancers. For some very subtle gestures of hands or legs, they can also express vivid images through painting techniques, endowing the characters in Dunhuang murals with spirituality, allowing people of today's era to experience the unique historical and cultural aspects of Xinjiang through these Dunhuang mural works, and feel the joy brought by music and dance.

(2) Music section

For the music part of Dunhuang murals, we mainly judge it through some unique musical instruments. The main characteristic of Dunhuang murals is that the painters love some large-scale music performances very much, so the music scenes drawn are usually mainly large-scale. However, the techniques and instruments held by each performer in Dunhuang murals are still vividly depicted by the painters in the murals. As future generations, we can also speculate on the music culture advocated by the people of the ancient period in the region based on the details of these paintings. The types of musical instruments displayed in Dunhuang murals are very diverse and complex, and even the same instrument may have certain differences in its form and performance methods in different historical periods. Common types of musical instruments include criticism, percussion instruments, flute instruments, xiao instruments, etc. These instruments buried in Dunhuang murals gradually outline the ancient music culture of Xinjiang region in modern society.

(3) Painting section

Although on the surface, there seems to be no connection between the painting style of Dunhuang murals and ethnic music, we can view this issue from a macro perspective. By extending the painting style of Dunhuang murals, we can effectively infer the way of life, folk customs, etc. of the people in Xinjiang region in ancient history. These humanistic information can help us better appreciate the ancient music culture of the region. Due to the unique geographical location of ancient Dunhuang, as the connecting point between the Central Plains and Xinjiang, this area is not only an important checkpoint on the entire Silk Road, but also a multi-ethnic region with complex and diverse folk cultures. Therefore, when we look at and appreciate Dunhuang wall paintings, we will find that their painting styles are very diverse, including not only some classical painting styles from the Central Plains, At the same time, we can also find some schools of foreign ethnic groups in Dunhuang murals. This multi-ethnic cultural exchange had a very profound impact and significance on Dunhuang at that time, and also laid a solid foundation for the progress and development of music culture in Xinjiang region.

3. Music element connection

(1) Musical Instruments

We also mentioned above that the depiction of musical instruments in Dunhuang murals is very rich and delicate. From Dunhuang murals, we can not only appreciate the performance scenes of many instruments, but also discover some unique pipa, flute, and xiao instruments in Xinjiang. Most of these instruments were introduced from Xinjiang and gradually promoted

and spread in mainland China. Ultimately, it was passed down as a traditional classical instrument in China for thousands of years. Taking pipa instruments as an example, in many Dunhuang murals, we can find the shadow of pipa instruments to some extent. Later generations often mistake these instruments for traditional classical Chinese instruments. Although this idea did not have much influence from the perspective of contemporary society, after historical analysis, pipa instruments were initially introduced from the Western Regions to the Central Plains. However, in the long river of history, it has been covered by the integration of ethnic cultures, and pipa instruments have gradually been included in Han culture.

In theory, the history of the appearance of pipa instruments is also very long. Therefore, we can see from Dunhuang murals that the forms of pipa instruments depicted by people of different periods are also slightly different. However, overall, the types of pipa instruments can be mainly divided into two types: one is the round and straight necked pipa, and the other is the pear shaped pipa connected to the resonance box. During the Qin and Han dynasties, the pipa instruments widely circulated in the Dunhuang region were mainly the first type. During the Sui and Tang dynasties, people often referred to pipa instruments as "pro Han" or "qin pipa". In fact, as early as the Eastern Han Dynasty, pipa instruments were recorded by the Confucian scholar Liu Xi in the book "Shi Ming" and referred to as "loquat". Although the name of this instrument gradually evolved from "loquat" to "pipa" for a long time, since it was originally introduced from the Western Regions, From this, we can deeply appreciate the profound impact of Western Regions culture on Central Plains culture. In addition to its name, we can further explore the performance form of pipa instruments from Dunhuang murals. Based on some descriptions in Dunhuang murals, we can preliminarily judge the instrument. Its initial performance form was performed on horseback in a dynamic marching manner. Based on the traditional cultural customs of Xinjiang, we can further determine that this instrument was created by the nomadic people of Xinjiang during their nomadic process. This instrument not only expresses their emotions, but also brings some joy to their nomadic life. Therefore, the pipa instrument has gradually been passed down. Nowadays, the vast majority of pipa performances we see are static performances. It is difficult to reproduce the form of the pipa played on horseback depicted in Dunhuang murals [7].

The Tang Dynasty in history was not only the peak period of China's economic strength, but also an important stage for the further promotion and development of pipa instruments. During this period, there were some outstanding pipa performers, such as Cao Gang, Kang Kunlun, Cao Bao, Duan Shanben, and so on. Among them, the Kang Kunlun performers were from the Kangju tribe in the Western Regions, which is a very representative and influential tribe in the Western Regions. Nowadays, the Kangju ethnic group has become a part of the Kazakh people, who mainly live in Xinjiang. From this perspective, we can see the inextricable connection between the music culture of

Xinjiang and the Dunhuang murals. These pipa players with high artistic attainments not only perform the pipa exquisitely, but also allow people to deeply appreciate the brilliance of pipa instruments. At the same time, it further promotes the music culture brought by pipa instruments, adding a rich and colorful touch to the traditional music history.

(2) Music and dance

In addition to the musical instruments we have enjoyed in Dunhuang murals mentioned above, the painters have also painted many beautiful dance postures unique to the region in Dunhuang murals. The dance postures depicted in Dunhuang murals are very rich, but they can still be divided into the following types based on their types: first, dance postures with Han people as the main body; Secondly, dance movements with the Western Regions as the main body; Thirdly, the dance style is mainly composed of Tianzhu, which has been passed down to the region [8]. Taking the dance posture of the Western Regions as an example, some of the dance postures depicted in Dunhuang murals are very vivid and vivid. People often imagine dynamic dance postures from static Dunhuang murals, among which a typical rotating dance posture is mainly manifested as the dancer's knees being slightly bent, hands raised above the head, while quickly rotating towards one side of the body. This dance posture was very popular during the Tang Dynasty. Due to the fact that this dance was introduced from the Western Regions to the Central Plains and its main feature is rotation, people also refer to it as the "Hu Xuan Dance". Tang Dynasty poet Bai Juyi once described the exquisite posture of Hu Xuan dance in his poem, "The heart responds to the strings, the hands respond to the drums, and the strings and drums are lifted with one sound." This poem mainly tells the scene of a dancer performing Hu Xuan dance accompanied by the drums. In addition, during the Tang Dynasty, An Lushan was also enthusiastic about performing the Hu Xuan dance. Although the figure's body size was relatively fat in history, it did not affect their dance posture. Some people described An Lushan as "as light as a swallow" when performing the Hu Xuan dance. Although it was slightly exaggerated, from the historical perspective of An Lushan, it can be seen that he was originally a person from the Western Regions, so it is natural to dance the Hu Xuan dance. From this perspective, there is indeed a very close connection between the Hu Xuan dance depicted in Dunhuang murals and the Western Regions.

In contemporary ethnic dance in Xinjiang, there is also a dance posture similar to the "Hu Xuan Dance", which mainly involves rotating dance movements. There was a legendary story passed down in Xinjiang, where a nearly 100 year old Uyghur man, due to his older age, needed the help of crutches for daily walking. However, when he heard the music of Hu Xuan Dance, he couldn't help but dance freely, and it can rotate for a long time, making some upright young people feel ashamed. Although we cannot verify the authenticity of this story, the love of the Uyghur people for the Hu Xuan dance is an undeniable fact. In history, the Uyghur people were mainly developed from tribes such as the Tiele, Gaoche, and Uyghur tribes, so there is a very

close connection between these tribes. The popular "Hu Xuan Dance" in the Tang Dynasty was also introduced from the Western Regions, so we can infer that the "Hu Xuan Dance" depicted in Dunhuang murals is closely related to the Western Regions region at that time - present-day Xinjiang region [10].

4. Conclusion

In summary, many of the scenes depicted in Dunhuang murals are set against the cultural background of the Western Regions, while the Western Regions in history mainly refer to the present-day Xinjiang region. From the above analysis, we can deeply feel that the communication and exchange of music and culture between the Western Regions and the Central Plains began very early in ancient history. And this mentality of mutual learning is also an important reason for the formation of today's rich and colorful ethnic music culture. We hope that the Xinjiang ethnic music culture contained in Dunhuang murals can be promoted and promoted for a longer time, and make greater contributions to the progress and development of China's folk culture field.

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